

X-Ray Diffractometric Studies on *N*-Hydroxy-*N*-aryl-arylamides

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The X-ray diffraction data of fifteen *N*-hydroxy-*N*-aryl-arylamides are described here, out of which 14 are reported for the first time. An attempt has been made to establish their diffraction patterns.

ALTHOUGH a considerable number of *N*-hydroxy-*N*-aryl-arylamides have been synthesised and their analytical potentialities have been explored^{1,2}, but the application of X-ray technique for the characterisation of powder patterns of these compounds is scarce. However, a report⁴ on X-ray powder pattern and index with *N*-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide (BHP), was brought out. Latter some sporadic literature on X-ray work of metal chelates of BHP appeared^{5,6}. In this work, for the first time, an attempt has been made to characterise the *N*-hydroxy-*N*-aryl-arylamides by plotting their X-ray diffraction patterns.

Experimental

A Philips X-ray diffraction unit (generator PW 1140 and vertical goniometer PW 1050/70) equipped with CuK α target tube ($\lambda=1.5405$ Å), graphite crystal monochromator, and flat bed strip chart recorder were used. Equipment was regulated to the following operating conditions: X-ray radiation intensity 40/20 kV/ma, goniometer rotation 1° 2 θ /min, scintillation counter energy frequency 4000 c/s, and chart speed 2°/min.

The samples were crystallised before use from the mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (1 : 1) and dried over P₂O₅ in vacuum. The final purity of all compounds was also checked by comparison of their melting points with those reported previously.

In an agate mortar 0.5 g of the sample was ground to a fine powder. A metallic slotted sample mount (15 mm × 20 mm × 1 mm) was taken and the slot of the mount was covered from one side with the help of a celluloid tape. The ground sample was compacted to a flat solid to ensure that the whole mount having an uniform bed compactness and thickness. The cooling water of the tube shield was

regulated to 4 kg/cm² and the rest of the equipment was tuned to the aforesaid conditions. The pure silicon standard sample was inserted into the sample holder and the relative intensity of SiK α was found out⁷, since this line is a function of the goniometer 2 θ setting. The silicon sample was subsequently removed and previously prepared experimental samples were inserted in the sample holder one at a time and scanned chronologically. The inter-planer distances of the lattice spacings were calculated as per Bragg's equation, $n\lambda=2d \sin \theta$.

Results and Discussion

The X-ray diffraction study of *N*-hydroxy-*N*-aryl-arylamides were new and their X-ray data cards are not yet available with ASTM^{8,9}. However, for this experimental work, BHP sample was first scanned and the values thus obtained were compared with the data available⁴. Table 1, reveals that the X-ray powder patterns of BHP and its 3 strongest lines obtained by authors are in close agreement with the data obtained by Chan and Moshier⁴, except some exceptions given as follows.

- (i) The first strongest line has shown a shift in d-spacing by 0.015 Å.
- (ii) The intensity of the second strongest line is 10 percent higher than the reported values. The shift in d-spacing is natural and this small shift is permissible in X-ray studies. The higher intensity values obtained may be attributed to the following basic reasons which are quite resonable and justified.
 - (a) The pattern obtained by Chan and Moshier⁴ was with the help of a classical XRD unit employing capillary technique and camera work, whereas authors have used monochromator and pulse height analysers, and

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF X-RAY DATA OF *N*-HYDROXY-*N*-PHENYLBENZAMIDE (BHP)

Sl. no.	Description	Ref. 4	Present study	
1.	Formula	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ NO ₂	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ NO ₂	
2.	Colour/Shape	Crystalline	White/Crystalline	
3.	Sample source	Prepared by reacting benzoyl chloride and phenylhydroxylamine	G. R. Product No. 8684 (E. Merck, India)	
4.	Crystallisation solvent	Ethanol	Benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1)	
5.	Equipment	General Electric XRD/3-5	Philips PW-1140	
6.	(a) X-Ray tube	Cu K α	Cu K α	
	(b) Tube power supply kV/mA	50/16	18/35	
7.	Technique	Capillary and camera work	Pulse height electronic counter and flat bed chart recorder	
8.	Observations	d Å	d Å	I/I ₀
	1st strong line	12.10	11.95	1.00
	2nd strong line	3.90	3.95	0.54
	3rd strong line	4.44	4.40	0.36

TABLE 2—XRD PATTERNS SHOWING 3 STRONG LINES OF THE *N*-HYDROXY-*N*-ARYL-ARYLAMIDES ALONGWITH THEIR INTER-PLANER SPACINGS AND RELATIVE INTENSITY RATIO

Sl. no.	R'	R''	R'—C—O R''—N—OH			I/I ₀		
			d Å					
1.	C ₆ H ₅	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	13.00	3.31	2.23	1.00	0.425	0.346
2.	2-CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	4.67	13.00	3.09	1.00	0.951	0.244
3.	3-CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	13.39	4.94	2.79	1.00	0.962	0.754
4.	4-CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	3.81	4.49	3.14	1.00	0.375	0.125
5.	3-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	5.79	3.85	3.72	1.00	0.268	0.244
6.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	14.36	3.92	2.17	1.00	0.302	0.210
7.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	3.62	3.22	3.69	1.00	0.531	0.429
8.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	4.44	3.72	3.23	1.00	0.913	0.913
9.	3-Br-C ₆ H ₄	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	5.95	6.71	3.92	1.00	0.545	0.545
10.	C ₆ H ₅ -CH ₂	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	4.23	4.05	3.85	1.00	0.245	0.206
11.	C ₆ H ₅ O-CH ₂	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	5.54	2.13	3.13	1.00	0.689	0.289
12.	CH ₃ -CH=CH	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	4.04	4.70	4.31	1.00	0.882	0.647
13.	2-C ₆ H ₅ O-CH=CH	C ₆ H ₅	3.83	7.69	4.65	1.00	0.670	0.470
14.	4-CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -CH=CH	C ₆ H ₅	5.50	3.30	3.86	1.00	0.920	0.62

(b) The relative intensity of samples may change on account of preferred orientation of the crystal in sample bed. This can be avoided by spinning the sample, but considering the high purity and compactness of the sample bed, specimens were not spinned.

Since repeated scanning of the BHP samples showed reproducible results and the XRD patterns were found to be identical, hence the standardisation and calibration were assumed to be satisfactory, and all *N*-hydroxy-*N*-aryl-arylamides were scanned one after another. The three strongest lines of each compound along with their d-spacing and relative intensity are compiled in Table 2 for comparative assessment.

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References

1. Y. K. AGRAWAL, *Russ. Chem. Rev. (Engl. Transl.)*, 1979, 48, 948; *Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 1980, 5, 3.
2. D. R. AGRAWAL and S. G. TANDON, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1972, 17, 257; *Croat. Chem. Acta*, 1981, 54, 115.
3. D. C. BHURA and S. G. TANDON, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1969, 14, 278; 1971, 16, 106.
4. F. L. CHAN and R. W. MOSHIER, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1961, 55, 26819 (U. S. Department of Commerce Office, Technical Service P. B. Report, 1959, No. 161, p. 496; WADC-TR-59-533).
5. F. J. KING and P. G. HARRISON, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1972, 815.
6. J. PARSON, W. T. BEHER and G. D. BAKER, *Henry Ford Hosp. Med. Bull.*, 1958, 6.
7. "Philips Scientific (Equipment) Application Data", Eindhoven, Netherlands, 1960, No. 1, pp. 1-40.
8. "Powder Diffraction File, JCPDS Search Manual, Organic Compounds", 1978.
9. J. D. HANAWALT, H. W. RINN and L. K. FREVEL, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal.*, 1938, 10, 457.
10. H. P. KLUG and L. E. ALEXANDER, "X-ray Diffraction Procedures for Polycrystalline and Amorphous Materials", Chapman and Hall, London, 1954.